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A deeply recessed platform of rock, quite overhung by the cliff and necessitating a climb to gain access—it can be reached now only by a 12ft. ladder—, provided an ideal "retreat" for the *Wanawāsa Bhikkhu*, or forest monks, who centuries ago made it their habitation.

For this cave dwelling was undoubtedly the ancient *pansala* of the Monastery located at this part of Dimbulā-gala.

It would be difficult to find any cave-sheltered residence of Buddhist monks, so long abandoned, which has survived the flight of time with lesser weathering by the elements, or wilful destruction by the later occupiers of the site.

Every available foot of the flat-floored cavern was pressed into service. A half-wall, run along the platform's edge and following all its curves, enclosed an area sufficiently roomy to permit of a cosy residence, walled up to the rock roof on south and east, allowing 22ft. by 15ft. for very commodious housing and, in addition, leaving room for a suitable verandah in front, with wider unconfined space on the east side.

The *pansala* had a doorway in the middle of each of its walled sides, and was lighted originally by two large windows (4ft. 5in. by 2ft. 4in.) with crossed wooden bars. The wonder is that one only has since been hacked away. The walls of the chamber even now are nearly 12ft. in height at one point, and the plaster is little damaged on the whole.

Two or three other caves occur under detached boulders between the hamlet and the cliff foot in which are Caves A and B. A short, poor, inscription is found at one (Cave C).¹⁹

KUDĀ ULPATA AND KOSGAHA ULPATA VILLAGERS.

Before leaving Dimbulā-gala and pushing further into the "Veḍi Raṭa" of Tamankaduwa as far as the utmost confines of the North Central Province on the South East, photographs of the inmates of the two hamlets, Kudā Ulpata and Kosgaha Ulpata, were secured.¹⁹

It is quite easy to single out, from each group, the members exhibiting in more or less degree a Veḍḍā strain. Intermarriage between those of Veḍḍā origin, and the unscrupulous Low-Country Sinhalese adventurers who have settled in these hamlets—to the sad undoing of their simple folk—is gradually destroying nearly all traces of pure Veḍḍā type.²⁰

The "purest Veḍḍā" in general characteristics (short stature, distinctive features, fuzzy hair, &c.), among these two communities was "Vélā" of Kosgaha Ulpata, who proved himself the brightest and most active of the Dimbulā-gala *Gam-Veḍḍō*.²¹

APPENDIX.

The several inscriptions referred to in the above account are grouped below, for more convenient reference.

1. MOLA-HITIYE-VELÉ-GALA.

Of the four rock-cut records,²² all of the same period, discovered at this site, the first and second (Nos. 1, 2) were manifestly intended to be read together (being enclosed within outline framing), and were doubtless both engraved during the reign of the King "Naka" named in the last line.

19. Plate XII; Kuda Ulpata and Kosgaha Ulpata Villagers.

20. Of such, in 1897, were Carols, Juwan, and two other *ex-detant* "Appubamis" of Matara District, Pabbis of Kelaniya, Colombo District, and several other like "vultures" from the Low-Country and Matale Districts, who had gradually scented the prey and swooped down on the few scattered Veḍḍā hamlets, under the specious plea of "trade" with these poverty-stricken demizens of Tamankaduwa's remotest nooks and corners.

21. See Plate IX. Among the Kuda Ulpata Villagers the third figure from the left was the *Aṭṭibī-ti*, or third Headman of the Veḍḍō. This exceptionally intelligent and willing young Veḍḍā, Vélā, was drowned a year or two later in trying to cross a swollen stream when the floods were out. He does not appear in the group.

22. Plate XIII.

The writing of these first two inscriptions is beautifully incised, in four lines of bold, deeply carved, characters, clear throughout, save for four *aksharas*, of which three are too worn to read except speculatively.

A *swastika* symbol, to left, precedes both records.

The employment of the "Cave type" palatal *ṣ* for *ṣagaṣa* (No. 2) in a Rock Epigraph is peculiar, but not unique; the dental *s* almost invariably rules on rock but not on caves, as, with this one exception, it does in these and the other two inscriptions.

Inscription No. 1.

The first inscription, in three lines, belongs to (Gamani) Abaya, or Gaja Báhu I. (A.D. 113-135), son of Kuta-kana or Vanka-násika ("Crooked Nosed")²³ Tisa (A.D. 110-113)—here alone given the prænomen "Jeta"—and grandson of Vasaba (A.D. 66-110), who, in this, and other records of the period, is styled "Devanapiya Tisa Maha Raja."²⁴

Text.

1. Sidham Devanapiya Tisa Maha Rajaha²⁴ marumanake Kuta
2. kana²³ Rajaha Jeta pute Raja Abaye Atara gagahi (.. ..) takaha Ati
3. (..) yeli Pavata Viharahi biku sagaye sovaṇa kota (ri)²⁵ niyate.

Translation.

Hail! King (Gamani) Abhaya, son of King Jettha (Tissa) the Crook-Nosed,²³ (and) grandson of the Great King (Vasaba) Tissa²¹ beloved of the gods (Devanampiya), ordered (that) a golden finial²⁵ (be fashioned) for the Community of Bhikkhus in Ati (..) yeli Parvata Vihara of (.. ..) taka at Atara-ganga.

Inscription No. 2.

This short record consists of but eleven *aksharas*, all perfect forming the fourth, or last, line within the oblong frame.

The King "Naka," who herein confirms the previous donation, was Mahallaka Naga of the Mahawaṇsa, either brother-in-law (*suhuru-baḍu*) or father-in-law (*sasuró*), of his immediate predecessor Gaja Báhu I.

Text.

Naka Maha Raje dina sagasa.

Translation.

The Great King (Mahallaka) Naga bestowed (this finial) on the (said) Community.

Inscription No. 3.

A shallowly cut record, of four lines: much weathered in places, and with portions possibly missing. Three vertical dots (also found elsewhere) precede "Naka-vili" after "sagaha."

It is extremely tantalising to have lost the letters, in line 3, which should have given us the name of Vanka-násika Tissa's Queen,²⁴ the likely donor of these tanks and fields to the Vihara.

23. Kuta-kana = *Kuteḥkāna* (Pali), 'halse (hooked nose). In the *Dīpa-vaṇsa* Makalan Tissa (B.C. 42-20), is called "Kutikanna Tissa."

24. If King Vasaba was not alternatively named "Tissa" (no inscription known to the writer has the combined names) *marumanake* must be translated 'descendant,' and the identity of this particular 'Devanapiya Tisa Maha Raja' left uncertain.

25. *Sovaṇa kotaru*. Translated (previously), 'golden finial.' The words are repeated in another inscription of Gaja Báhu at Anurādhapura; and in one of his granddaughters, Vasaba, at Sadiya-gala North Central Province. *Kuta* assumed = *Iduru* (See *Epigraphia Zeylanica* I p. 227.)